

Demonstration of direct air capture of CO₂ using microalgae raceway reactors

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ABSTRACT

The continuous increase in atmospheric CO₂ concentration underscores the urgent need for scalable and energy-efficient carbon removal technologies. This study demonstrates, for the first time, the implementation of a tailored Direct Air Capture (DAC) concept integrated within large-scale microalgae raceway reactors, enabling direct CO₂ uptake from ambient air without external gas supply. A 600 m² reactor operated continuously with *Scenedesmus* sp. maintained stable productivity (12 g m⁻² day⁻¹) under extreme carbon limitation (TIC ≈ 20 mg L⁻¹, pH ≈ 10). Fine-bubble aeration in the sump achieved nearly complete CO₂ removal from air streams, while passive absorption across the raceway and paddlewheel sections provided almost all the carbon required for biomass growth. The overall CO₂ removal efficiency reached 95%, confirming the reactor's operation as a functional bio-DAC system. The estimated energy demand for air bubbling (≈ 2.9 kWh kg⁻¹ CO₂) is comparable to or below that of current engineered DAC technologies. This approach establishes a low-cost, renewable-compatible, and scalable pathway for atmospheric CO₂ capture that couples negative-emission performance with biomass production, laying the groundwork for decentralized, carbon-negative biotechnological systems contributing to global greenhouse-gas mitigation.

1. Introduction

The continuous rise in global temperature caused by greenhouse gas emissions, particularly CO₂, demands effective strategies to mitigate their impact. Conventional measures—such as improving combustion efficiency, reducing fossil fuel use, and implementing Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS)—help limit future emissions but cannot remove CO₂ already accumulated in the atmosphere [1]. Hence, increasing attention is given to Negative Emission Technologies (NETs), including Direct Air Capture (DAC), which can actively extract CO₂ from air [2,3]. As noted by Sandalow et al. [4], NET portfolios should integrate both engineered and biological solutions, with algal DAC systems offering additional benefits in energy integration and land use.

Direct Air Capture (DAC) relies on a range of physicochemical separation processes to selectively isolate CO₂ from ambient air, including liquid solvent absorption systems based on alkaline solutions or amines,

solid adsorbent-based technologies employing porous or functionalized materials, and more recently membrane-based separation processes using polymeric or facilitated-transport membranes designed to operate under atmospheric CO₂ concentrations [2,3,5–7]. Additional approaches, such as electrochemical DAC exploiting pH- or redox-swing mechanisms, are also emerging as potentially lower-temperature alternatives [8]. Despite significant technological progress, all engineered DAC routes remain constrained by high energy demand, regeneration requirements, and material costs, which currently limit large-scale deployment and motivate the exploration of biologically integrated alternatives [9].

However, recent studies demonstrate that coupling DAC with bio-based CO₂ utilization can markedly reduce energy demand and operational costs through process integration [10,11], reinforcing its role as a key technology for achieving net-negative emissions and long-term climate mitigation. Moreover, techno-economic analyses indicate that

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the large-scale deployment of DAC remains constrained by high energy requirements and material costs, with current capture estimates exceeding 300 USD t⁻¹ CO₂ [6,7,12]. These challenges highlight the need for low-energy, bio-assisted DAC solutions that leverage renewable energy and natural absorption mechanisms.

Microalgae are photosynthetic microorganisms renowned for their high capacity to fix carbon dioxide (CO₂). Stoichiometrically, approximately 1.8 kg of CO₂ is required to produce 1 kg of microalgal biomass. Considering that large-scale systems can achieve productivities of up to 100 tons ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, the corresponding CO₂ fixation potential can reach 200 tons ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, ranking microalgae among the most efficient biological systems for carbon capture [13,14]. Traditionally, microalgae production relies on pure CO₂ or CO₂-enriched gas streams derived from combustion or fermentation processes. Under these conditions, the high CO₂ concentration and its relatively high solubility in water promote rapid transfer into the culture medium. Nevertheless, even when using concentrated gas sources, maintaining efficient gas–liquid mass transfer remains a major operational challenge [15]. To address this limitation, numerous studies have explored engineering strategies such as gas recirculation, optimized sump design, and the use of closed or hybrid photobioreactor configurations to enhance carbonation efficiency [16–18]. These advances are essential for enabling the reliable and scalable application of microalgae as a sustainable CO₂ capture and utilization technology. Recent reviews further emphasize that the CO₂ fixation potential of microalgae depends not only on species selection but also on process optimization, where mass transfer and pH control remain the main rate-limiting steps for large-scale deployment [19].

A major challenge in advancing microalgae-based carbon capture technologies lies in enabling these systems to effectively remove CO₂ directly from ambient air, where concentrations are extremely low (~420 ppm) and gas–liquid mass transfer is inherently limited [1]. Achieving this goal requires transforming conventional production systems into functional Direct Air Capture (DAC) units that can operate autonomously, without dependence on external CO₂ sources. Among the available reactor designs, open raceway ponds stand out as the most promising due to their simple construction, low capital cost, and proven scalability for large-area deployment. Raceway algal pond systems have demonstrated stable operation at large scale for wastewater and CO₂ capture applications, confirming their robustness and adaptability under variable outdoor conditions [20]. Their extensive surface exposure to the atmosphere naturally facilitates gas exchange—both oxygen release and CO₂ absorption—but the overall efficiency of this process depends strongly on factors such as hydrodynamics, temperature, solar irradiance, and, particularly, pH.

Alkaline conditions can substantially increase the absorption of atmospheric CO₂ by shifting the carbonate equilibrium toward bicarbonate and carbonate species, thereby maintaining a concentration gradient that favors gas transfer [21]. Nevertheless, because the gas–liquid mass transfer coefficient (*K_{ia}*) for CO₂ under ambient conditions is typically very low, the flux of CO₂ from air alone is generally insufficient to sustain high biomass productivities. To overcome this limitation, many large-scale raceways incorporate auxiliary units such as sumps or “degasser” sections, where gas–liquid contact is intensified through bubbling or mechanical agitation [22]. These sumps are primarily designed to remove excess dissolved oxygen—a common issue in dense cultures—but have also proven effective in improving CO₂ transfer when concentrated gas streams or flue gases are supplied [23]. However, their potential role as passive air–liquid contactors for capturing CO₂ directly from the atmosphere has not yet been systematically investigated, representing a critical knowledge gap that this study seeks to address.

In this study, we investigate the potential of open raceway pond reactors to function as integrated systems for Direct Air Capture (DAC) of CO₂ directly from the atmosphere. The analysis focuses on quantifying CO₂ transfer dynamics and establishing the complete CO₂ mass balance in a 600 m² pilot-scale reactor operated continuously under outdoor conditions, where ambient air served as the sole carbon source for

microalgal growth. Particular attention is given to evaluating how key operational parameters—such as pH and airflow rate—affect both the reactor’s capacity to absorb CO₂ from the air and its ability to meet the biological carbon requirements of the microalgae population. By combining experimental measurements with mass transfer modeling, this work identifies the operational thresholds and reactor design features necessary to sustain biomass productivity under carbon-limited conditions. The results presented are derived from real-environment operation, providing one of the first quantitative demonstrations of large-scale microalgae production driven exclusively by atmospheric CO₂. The findings not only validate the technical feasibility of this approach but also support the optimization and upscaling of the patented CHLYDRO technology (WO2024245917), designed to enable decentralized and energy-efficient CO₂ removal. Ultimately, this research contributes to the development of autonomous, low-cost biotechnological platforms capable of achieving net-negative carbon emissions in remote or off-grid regions, positioning microalgae-based DAC as a viable component of global carbon mitigation strategies.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Microorganism and culture medium

The raceway was inoculated with the microalgae strain *Scenedesmus* sp. This particular strain was chosen for its resilience and adaptability, as it is highly tolerant of fluctuating growth conditions and resistant to common contaminations and grazers. The assays were conducted using a specific culture medium, known as Mann & Myers medium. This medium was prepared with reclaimed water and supplemented with a precise mix of fertilizers (0.9 g·L⁻¹ NaNO₃, 0.14 g·L⁻¹ KH₂(PO₄), 0.18 g·L⁻¹ Mg(SO₄)₂ and 0.02 g·L⁻¹ Karentol (Konegard, Spain)). The inoculum for the reactor was produced in a parallel raceway reactor of 100 m² operated in continuous mode using freshwater and fertilizers following the same recipe as before. The inlet reclaimed freshwater exhibited an initial dissolved inorganic carbon concentration of 100 mg L⁻¹ at pH 8.0–8.2.

2.2. Raceway reactors

The experiments were conducted in a 600 m² raceway reactor located at the “CIESOL” Research Centre in Almería, Spain (36° 48′N–2° 43′W) (Fig. 1). The reactor design includes four channels, each 38 m long, 4 m wide, and 0.46 m high. The total culture volume is 105 m³, which is circulated through a 6.3 m³ sump located 2 m into one of the channels. The sump itself has a diameter of 2 m and is 2 m deep. A comprehensive monitoring and control system was implemented to manage the reactor’s key parameters. Probes for culture pH, temperature, and dissolved oxygen (DO) were connected to a control-transmitter unit (MM44) from Crison Instruments. The DO probe was specifically positioned at the end of a channel, just before the paddlewheel, to capture the most significant daily fluctuations. CO₂ probes from Vaisala were used to monitor the atmospheric gas and the gas outlet from the sump (Indigo, Vaisala). Data from these probes, along with a mass flow meter (PFM 725SF01-F, SMC) for measuring air flow, were managed by DAQFactory software.

Air was supplied to the reactor at a 300 mbar overpressure using a blower. This air was delivered through fine bubble diffusers (AFT2100, ECOTEC), which produced bubbles with a diameter smaller than 2 mm and an estimated residence time of 5–10 s within the sump. Notably, neither the pH nor the temperature of the culture was actively controlled during the experiments. A Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) system, based on a distributed architecture, enabled real-time monitoring and control. This system integrated all the sensors for culture monitoring as well as meteorological inputs like solar radiation, air temperature, and wind speed. All sensors sampled data every 10 s, allowing the system to detect rapid process fluctuations and support

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the experimental setup used in this study (top), showing the main reactor elements and air–liquid contact zones, and photograph of the 600 m² raceway reactor operating under outdoor conditions (bottom).

adaptive control strategies. Data were managed by a central control unit and visualized via a human-machine interface (HMI) for remote supervision and alarm management [24].

The raceway reactor was operated at a constant culture depth of 0.15 m in a semi-continuous mode. A fixed dilution rate of 0.2 day⁻¹ was applied to maintain a target biomass concentration of 0.8 g/L, although the final biomass concentration was lower, ranging from 0.4 to 0.6 g/L. To achieve this, a portion of the biomass was harvested daily, and fresh medium was added to the reactor. The daily addition of freshwater compensated for evaporative losses. Biomass concentration was measured every morning before harvesting. This was done by filtering 40 mL aliquots of the culture through a pre-dried 0.45 μm filter (Macherey-Nagel). The filters were then dried in an oven at 80°C for 24 h to determine the dry weight. The nutrient content of the culture supernatant was also evaluated daily to ensure that nutrient limitations did not occur, and fertilizers were added as needed. Total inorganic carbon (TIC) was determined on filtered culture samples by acidification to convert all inorganic carbon species into CO₂, followed by quantification of the released CO₂ using a Shimadzu TIC analyzer, according to standard analytical procedures.

2.3. Mass transfer and mass balance into the reactor

The CO₂ mass transfer and overall carbon balance in the raceway reactor were determined following the methodology described by Arraga et al. [25], adapted to the specific configuration of the present system. The approach combines experimental determination of local mass transfer coefficients (*K_ia*) with theoretical estimation of the driving

force for CO₂ exchange between the culture broth and the surrounding air, considering the physicochemical equilibrium of the carbonate system and the culture pH.

In open raceway reactors, CO₂ transfer between the gas and liquid phases occurs simultaneously in several sections of the system: (i) the sump, where air bubbling enhances gas–liquid contact through fine bubbles; (ii) the paddlewheel region, characterized by high turbulence and surface renewal; and (iii) the open channel, where diffusion and convective exchange with the atmosphere dominate. Each of these zones contributes differently to the total CO₂ flux depending on hydrodynamic conditions, interfacial area, and local chemical equilibrium. The mass transfer rate of CO₂ (*r_{CO₂}*) in each section was expressed by Eq. 1, where *K_La* (s⁻¹) is the overall volumetric mass transfer coefficient, *C_{CO₂}*^{*} (mg L⁻¹) is the equilibrium CO₂ concentration corresponding to the partial pressure of CO₂ in air, and *C_{CO₂}* (mg L⁻¹) is the actual dissolved CO₂ concentration in the culture broth. The latter was determined from the total inorganic carbon (TIC) concentration and the relative distribution of carbonate species, which depend on the culture pH and temperature. The equilibrium concentration of CO₂ in water was calculated using Henry's law (Eq. 2) where *H_{CO₂}* is the Henry constant (mol m⁻³ Pa⁻¹) corrected for temperature, and *p_{CO₂}* is the partial pressure of CO₂ in the gas phase (typically 400 ppm). The instantaneous *C_{CO₂}* was obtained from the measured TIC and pH, using the carbonate equilibrium constants *K₁* and *K₂* for the dissociation of carbonic acid, according to Eq. 3. The volumetric mass transfer coefficients (*K_ia*) for each section were determined experimentally from oxygen desorption and absorption tests following Arraga et al. [25]. The coefficients were adjusted for the respective diffusivities of the gases in water, using the ratio of diffusion

coefficients (D_{CO_2}/D_{O_2})^{0.5}. Paddlewheel and channel exhibit constant K_{ia} values of 160 and 1 h⁻¹, respectively, whereas the value into the sump is a function of air flow rate, values up to 208 h⁻¹ being measured at maximum of 500 L/min.

$$N_{CO_2} = K_L a (C_{CO_2}^* - C_{CO_2}) \quad (1)$$

$$C_{CO_2}^* = H_{CO_2} p_{CO_2} \quad (2)$$

$$C_{CO_2} = \frac{TIC}{1 + \frac{K_1}{[H^+]} + \frac{K_1 K_2}{[H^+]^2}} \quad (3)$$

The overall CO₂ balance for the system was then established as the sum of all gaseous and aqueous fluxes, including biological production/consumption by respiration/photosynthesis during night and daylight periods. This was estimated from dissolved oxygen measurements following the methodology proposed by [25]. Positive values denote CO₂ inputs (absorption or respiration), and negative values denote CO₂ removal (photosynthetic fixation or degassing). The CO₂ released by respiration was estimated indirectly from nighttime dissolved oxygen consumption rates, assuming aerobic respiration and a respiratory quotient close to unity, thereby allowing conversion of oxygen uptake into equivalent CO₂ production. The volumetric gas–liquid mass transfer coefficients (K_{ia}) for the paddlewheel and open-channel sections were obtained from experimental oxygen transfer measurements performed in the same raceway configuration and subsequently scaled to CO₂ using diffusivity-based correlations. Chemical enhancement of CO₂ absorption was not explicitly included in the K_{ia} values, as under atmospheric CO₂ concentrations the overall uptake rate is primarily governed by physical mass transfer, while the effect of carbonate chemistry is accounted for through the pH-dependent driving force expressed in terms of dissolved inorganic carbon.

3. Results and discussion

For clarity, this section is structured to clearly distinguish between results derived from theoretical calculations and mass balance modelling, and those obtained from experimental operation of the large-scale raceway reactor.

3.1. Theoretical CO₂ demand and carbon balance in large-scale raceway reactors

This subsection presents results derived from stoichiometric calculations and mass balance modelling. To analyze the potential of microalgae for direct air capture processes, it is important to fix the boundary conditions for this process on a large scale. Thus, in microalgae production systems, CO₂ is supplied both to maintain the culture pH within the optimal range and to provide the inorganic carbon required for photosynthesis, considering that approximately 45% of the dry biomass corresponds to carbon assimilated from the supplied CO₂. Under typical outdoor conditions, biomass productivities in open raceway ponds range from 10 to 25 g m⁻² day⁻¹, although optimized systems operated in warm climates and with efficient mixing can achieve values up to 40 g m⁻² day⁻¹ [14,26]. The CO₂ utilization efficiency—defined as the fraction of supplied carbon actually fixed into biomass—typically lies between 30% and 60%, depending on reactor design, mixing intensity, and pH control, with higher efficiencies obtained under optimized gas transfer and recirculation conditions [17,27]). However, by implementing advanced monitoring and control strategies, such as model-based pH regulation and adaptive CO₂ dosing, carbon utilization efficiencies close to 100% can be achieved, ensuring nearly complete assimilation of the injected CO₂ [28]. Comparable improvements in process efficiency have been observed in microalgae–wastewater systems where advanced nutrient and pH control strategies were implemented [29]. The unit cost of CO₂ supply for large-scale microalgae

production generally averages around €150 per ton CO₂, representing one of the major operational expenses (Acién et al., 2017).

These figures are relevant because they determine the boundary conditions for CO₂ supply in microalgae reactors. Thus, for a raceway reactor with a surface area of 600 m², and assuming a biomass productivity between 10 and 25 g m⁻² day⁻¹, the theoretical CO₂ consumption—calculated using the stoichiometric ratio of 1.8 kg CO₂ per kg biomass—ranges from 10.8 to 27.0 kg CO₂ day⁻¹ (Fig. 2). The CO₂ demand was calculated on a dry biomass basis, assuming a typical carbon content of microalgal biomass of 45–50% (w/w), which corresponds to an equivalent fixation of approximately 1.8 kg CO₂ per kg of dry biomass. When considering CO₂ utilization efficiencies between 30% and 100%, the actual CO₂ supply required to sustain biomass growth increases significantly. For instance, at a productivity of 25 g m⁻² day⁻¹, the effective CO₂ input would vary from 27 kg CO₂ day⁻¹ at full utilization to 225 kg CO₂ day⁻¹ at 30% efficiency. This translates into a carbon supply cost ranging from €0.27 to €2.25 per kg of biomass. This wide variability underscores the critical influence of CO₂ utilization efficiency on both the carbon footprint and economic performance of microalgae production. Because CO₂ represents a substantial share of the total operating cost, inefficient utilization can significantly increase the final biomass cost and reduce process sustainability.

3.2. Expected CO₂ exchange with the atmosphere under alkaline conditions

The following analysis is based on theoretical equilibrium and mass transfer considerations. To satisfy the carbon requirements of the culture, CO₂-rich gases are typically supplied to microalgae reactors; however, the dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) already present or introduced with the culture medium also makes a relevant contribution. This inorganic carbon, mainly in the form of bicarbonate and carbonate ions, participates in the bicarbonate buffer system, which regulates both the concentration of dissolved CO₂ and the equilibrium with atmospheric CO₂. The dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) supplied with the culture medium does not originate from equilibrium with atmospheric CO₂, but from the natural alkalinity and inorganic carbon content of the freshwater used, which, under the alkaline operating conditions of the reactor (pH ≈ 10), is predominantly stored as bicarbonate and carbonate species, leading to DIC levels substantially higher than those attainable in freshwater equilibrated with air. Depending on the pH of the culture, the dissolved CO₂ concentration may be higher or lower than the equilibrium value with the atmosphere, leading either to CO₂ stripping or CO₂ absorption. From a chemical perspective, CO₂ capture in alkaline microalgae raceway reactors is governed by the carbonate–bicarbonate equilibrium of the culture medium, which effectively acts as a dynamic absorbent system. At elevated pH, dissolved CO₂ is rapidly converted into bicarbonate and carbonate species, lowering the free CO₂ concentration in the liquid phase and maintaining a strong driving force for continuous absorption of atmospheric CO₂. This absorbed inorganic carbon is subsequently consumed by photosynthesis, thereby regenerating the absorbent capacity of the medium in situ. In contrast to conventional DAC systems relying on external sorbents, this biologically assisted mechanism couples CO₂ absorption, regeneration, and utilization within a single process, with gas–liquid contact zones such as the sump, paddlewheel, and open channels enhancing mass transfer efficiency.

At low pH values (< 9), a significant fraction of inorganic carbon exists as dissolved CO₂ and carbonic acid, producing a positive gradient of CO₂ partial pressure between the culture and the air. Under these conditions, the reactor behaves as a CO₂ emitter, losing carbon mainly through stripping in the open channels and turbulence zones such as the paddlewheel. In the present case, at pH 8, the theoretical CO₂ demand for biomass synthesis (21 kg day⁻¹) increased to 52 kg day⁻¹ due to stripping losses of 18 kg day⁻¹ in the channel and 23 kg day⁻¹ at the paddlewheel, while only 11 kg day⁻¹ was supplied with the culture

Fig. 2. Influence of biomass productivity and CO₂ utilization efficiency on the CO₂ consumption of the 600 m² raceway reactor.

medium (Fig. 3). Conversely, at high pH values (> 11), most inorganic carbon is converted into bicarbonate and carbonate species, resulting in almost negligible free CO₂ concentrations in the liquid. The partial pressure of CO₂ in the culture becomes lower than that in the atmosphere, thereby promoting passive CO₂ absorption from the air. At pH 10, the net CO₂ demand was reduced to 7.4 kg day⁻¹, since atmospheric absorption reached 1.6 kg day⁻¹ in the channel and 2.1 kg day⁻¹ at the paddlewheel, while 10.6 kg day⁻¹ was still provided with the culture medium (Fig. 3). Although pH values above 11 are discussed here as a theoretical upper limit for maximizing atmospheric CO₂ absorption, such conditions are generally unfavorable for microalgal growth, as they strongly limit CO₂ availability and nutrient bioavailability and can induce physiological stress; accordingly, the reactor in this study was operated at lower pH values (≈9.7–10.2) compatible with stable growth of *Scenedesmus* spp.

Overall, the results highlight that the pH-dependent carbonate equilibrium governs the direction and magnitude of CO₂ fluxes in raceway reactors. At lower pH values, CO₂ stripping dominates, substantially increasing the apparent CO₂ demand, whereas at higher pH values, bicarbonate buffering and atmospheric absorption mitigate carbon losses. These findings confirm that pH is critical to minimize CO₂ emissions and optimize carbon utilization efficiency in large-scale open raceway systems [23,30,31]. This agrees with previous studies showing

that pH not only regulates carbonate equilibria but also affects nutrient availability and overall reactor performance [32,33], underscoring the importance of pH control for maintaining both CO₂ capture and biomass productivity.

3.3. Experimental performance of the 600 m² raceway reactor under DAC operation

This subsection reports experimental results obtained during continuous operation of the 600 m² raceway reactor. The pH also plays a critical role in determining the biomass productivity of microalgal cultures. Most microalgae species exhibit optimal growth under near-neutral to slightly alkaline conditions (pH 7–8.5), beyond which growth rates progressively decline. At higher pH values, above 9.5, both CO₂ availability and nutrient solubility decrease, limiting photosynthetic carbon fixation and thereby reducing productivity. When no external CO₂ is supplied—or under severe CO₂-limiting conditions—the pH of the culture tends to rise naturally until a balance is reached between CO₂ supply from the atmosphere and CO₂ consumption by photosynthesis. In the case of *Scenedesmus* sp. cultivated in the 600 m² raceway reactor, the pH increased to values of 10.0, leading to a reduction in biomass productivity to approximately 12 g m⁻² day⁻¹ (Fig. 4). Under these conditions, the theoretical CO₂ demand

Fig. 3. Effect of pH on the modeled CO₂ exchange with the atmosphere in the different reactor sections (channel, paddlewheel, and sump) and on the overall CO₂ balance of the 600 m² raceway reactor.

Fig. 4. CO₂ supply–demand analysis for the 600 m² raceway reactor operated at an average bulk pH of 10 and a biomass productivity of 12 g m⁻² day⁻¹, showing the relative contributions of atmospheric absorption and dissolved inorganic carbon.

corresponding to this productivity is 13.0 kg CO₂ day⁻¹. This demand is partially met by the inorganic carbon (DIC) already present in the culture medium, contributing with 8.8 kg CO₂ day⁻¹. In addition, natural atmospheric absorption provides a small but relevant contribution, with 1.5 kg CO₂ day⁻¹ absorbed across the open channel and 1.9 kg CO₂ day⁻¹ through the paddlewheel region. Altogether, these sources account for 12.2 kg CO₂ day⁻¹, leaving a net external CO₂ requirement of 0.8 kg day⁻¹ to sustain the observed productivity. To meet this unmet demand, different CO₂ sourcing strategies can be considered.

The use of pure CO₂ is the most common approach in high-value biomass production due to its precise control and reliability [34], but it involves high operational costs and depends on a consistent logistics chain for gas delivery—often impractical for decentralized or remote sites. Alternatively, the use of industrial flue gases represents a more sustainable and environmentally beneficial option, simultaneously contributing to greenhouse gas mitigation through flue gas valorization [35]. Nevertheless, this approach imposes spatial and infrastructural constraints, as reactors must be located near emission sources equipped with suitable gas-cleaning systems. A third and increasingly attractive alternative is the direct air capture (DAC) of atmospheric CO₂, which can be seamlessly integrated with open microalgae systems [11,36]. Similar biological DAC approaches have been proposed by Singh and Saxena [37], who demonstrated that coupling atmospheric CO₂ absorption with biomass production can reduce capture costs and enhance overall process sustainability through integrated bioenergy systems. Based on the CO₂ concentration in ambient air, approximately 700 L·min⁻¹ of air would need to be processed to extract the 0.8 kg CO₂ day⁻¹ required in this case.

Moreover, enhancing CO₂ input from ambient air would not only lower the culture pH but also increase biomass productivity, thereby improving the overall CO₂ capture efficiency of the system. While DAC offers the advantage of site independence and aligns with long-term carbon neutrality goals, its technical maturity and energy costs remain significant challenges, especially for large-scale implementation. This comparative evaluation emphasizes that the choice of CO₂ source is not only a technical decision but also one that profoundly impacts production costs, operational logistics, and environmental footprint. Tailoring the CO₂ supply strategy to the scale, location, and economic goals of the production system is thus essential for maximizing efficiency and sustainability.

Direct Air Capture (DAC) technologies, regardless of the specific approach, inherently require significant energy input and capital investment in infrastructure. This is due to the fundamental challenge of separating CO₂ from atmospheric air, where its concentration is extremely low—approximately 0.8 g CO₂ per cubic meter of air. Among

the most widely explored and potentially scalable DAC technologies are selective membrane systems and adsorption/desorption processes using solid or liquid sorbents. These technologies are currently considered among the most promising in terms of selectivity and efficiency, yet they remain complex and costly, largely because of the energy required for regeneration and gas compression, as well as the materials and maintenance demands of the systems involved. An alternative and more integrated approach to DAC involves utilizing the existing architecture of raceway reactors, particularly the sump section, as a functional CO₂ absorber. If properly designed and operated, the sump can serve as an effective air–liquid contact zone for CO₂ absorption from ambient air.

3.4. Experimental determination of CO₂ capture efficiency and mass transfer

In the case study evaluated here, a sump with a diameter of 2.0 m and a depth of 2.0 m was equipped with eight low-pressure diffusers, enabling uniform air dispersion. Various airflow rates were tested, and the CO₂ concentrations at the inlet and outlet of the gas phase were continuously monitored to assess the capture efficiency. Results demonstrated that the CO₂ concentration in the air exiting the sump dropped consistently to near-zero values, with outlet concentrations in the range of 20–30 ppm, irrespective of the inlet airflow rate (Fig. 5). These values indicate that nearly all the CO₂ entering the system was transferred to the liquid phase, under the operational conditions tested (pH = 10, TIC = 100 mg/L). CO₂ removal efficiencies of up to 95% were observed, confirming the sump's capability as a highly effective passive DAC unit integrated within the production system. However, the total amount of CO₂ transferred remains directly dependent on the volume of air processed, with values ranging from 7 to 25 g/h. While increasing the air flow rate would theoretically allow for greater absolute CO₂ capture, in this specific setup, physical limitations of the existing facility prevented higher flow rates from being implemented. Despite this constraint, the findings validate that raceway reactor sumps can serve dual purposes—both as traditional CO₂ delivery points and as passive atmospheric CO₂ absorbers, offering a cost-effective and infrastructure-efficient solution for supplementing inorganic carbon in open algal production systems.

To better understand the mechanisms underlying direct air capture (DAC) of CO₂ in raceway reactors, a detailed analysis of the daily variation of culture conditions was conducted under real operating conditions. The system was operated in continuous mode, using ambient air as the sole source of CO₂, which was introduced via air bubbling in the sump. Throughout the day, different airflow rates from zero to 500 L/min were applied at specific intervals, as previously described [25], to

Fig. 5. Experimentally determined CO₂ capture efficiency and capture capacity in the sump of the 600 m² raceway reactor as a function of air flow rate under alkaline conditions (average bulk pH = 10, TIC = 100 mg L⁻¹).

experimentally determine the mass transfer capacity and photosynthesis rate. Results indicate that both culture temperature and dissolved oxygen concentration followed a diurnal pattern, closely aligned with the solar radiation profile (Fig. 6A). The temperature remains in the range of 22–35°C, which was reported to be adequate for *Scenedesmus* sp. The operating temperature range of 22–35 °C corresponds to the typical outdoor conditions at the experimental site and to the optimal or near-optimal growth window of *Scenedesmus* spp.; at lower temperatures photosynthetic and metabolic rates decrease, while sustained temperatures above ~35–38 °C may induce thermal stress and reduced culture stability, although alternative microalgal species adapted to colder or hotter climates could be selected for site-specific operation. The system exhibited peak dissolved oxygen concentrations up to 17 mg O₂/L, which is consistent with typical values in raceway reactors supporting active biomass growth. This suggests that photosynthetic activity remained robust under the tested conditions.

When examining the CO₂ composition at the inlet and outlet of the sump, a modest fluctuation was observed in the inlet CO₂ concentration, primarily due to natural variations in atmospheric conditions (Fig. 6B). In contrast, the CO₂ concentration in the outlet gas stream consistently remained near zero throughout the day. This outlet profile followed a sinusoidal pattern, characterized by non-detectable values during daylight hours and slightly elevated concentrations during nighttime, reflecting the reduced photosynthetic CO₂ uptake and the onset of respiratory CO₂ release. The pH of the culture showed a pronounced diel variation. During the night, pH declined due to CO₂ accumulation from cellular respiration. In contrast, during the daylight period, the pH increased significantly as a result of CO₂ consumption through photosynthesis. The pH oscillated within a range of 9.7–10.2, a variation that reflects the dynamic balance between CO₂ capture and biological utilization. These observations confirm that the rate of CO₂ supplied via air bubbling in the sump was insufficient to fully satisfy the culture's CO₂ demand, especially during periods of high photosynthetic activity. Nevertheless, the pH remained within an acceptable operational window, suggesting that partial atmospheric CO₂ capture and carbon recycling within the reactor were sufficient to sustain biomass growth. Notably, the system maintained stable performance in continuous mode, with a dilution rate of 0.2 day⁻¹ and biomass concentrations ranging from 0.4 to 0.6 g/L throughout the experiment. These results provide strong evidence that raceway reactors equipped with air-driven DAC through sump bubbling can support continuous microalgal production even under CO₂-limited conditions, although careful adjustment of airflow and operational parameters is required to ensure carbon balance and pH stability.

By processing the experimental data collected during the continuous operation of the raceway reactor, it is possible to quantify both the CO₂ capture capacity as mass of CO₂ captured per unit time and the CO₂ removal efficiency. Results demonstrate that the CO₂ capture capacity is dependent on the airflow rate provided to the sump, with observed values ranging from 5 to 25 g CO₂/h (Fig. 6C). These values are fully consistent with those obtained in previous short-term experiments, confirming the repeatability and robustness of the capture mechanism under continuous operation. Importantly, the CO₂ capture rate remained stable throughout the day, indicating that it is governed primarily by mass transfer dynamics rather than temporal changes in biological activity or solar radiation. While pH is known to influence the driving force for CO₂ transfer—as discussed previously—the pH values during the experiment remained relatively stable, averaging close to pH 10. This narrow range limits the variability in driving force, helping to isolate the impact of airflow rate on capture capacity. Slight variations were observed in CO₂ removal efficiency, which was calculated as the percentage of CO₂ transferred from the air into the liquid phase. During the daylight period, when photosynthetic activity and pH are at their peak, CO₂ removal efficiency approached 100%, reflecting optimal absorption conditions (Fig. 6C). During the night period, when biological CO₂ uptake ceases and respiratory CO₂ is released, the removal efficiency declined slightly, averaging around 90%. This minor reduction is attributed to the additional endogenous CO₂ produced by respiration, which accumulates in the culture broth and slightly diminishes the driving force for further CO₂ absorption.

3.5. Comparison between theoretical predictions and experimental observations

Experimental data allow for the analysis of the main phenomena occurring within the reactor and the separate quantification of the CO₂ mass balance in the system. Results confirm that during the night, respiration generates approximately 300 g CO₂ h⁻¹, which accumulates in the reactor because, due to the high pH, it is not stripped to the atmosphere (Fig. 7A). Additionally, during the night there is a net CO₂ uptake from the atmosphere of 54 g h⁻¹ through the channel and 52 g h⁻¹ through the paddlewheel, while CO₂ capture in the sump ranges from 5 to 14 g h⁻¹. During the daylight period, photosynthetic activity reverses the CO₂ flux—from production to consumption—reaching values as low as -1800 g h⁻¹. This demand is partially compensated by the increased CO₂ supply through the sump, where higher airflow rates (up to 30 g h⁻¹) were applied, and by additional atmospheric absorption through the channel and paddlewheel, accounting for 43 and 39 g h⁻¹,

Fig. 6. Daily variation of operating conditions and CO₂ capture performance in the 600 m² raceway reactor operated under DAC conditions: (A) culture temperature, dissolved oxygen, and solar radiation; (B) inlet and outlet CO₂ concentrations in the sump together with the corresponding pH evolution; and (C) CO₂ capture rate and removal efficiency as a function of the air flow rate supplied to the sump.

respectively. Moreover, the supply of fresh culture medium containing dissolved inorganic carbon contributes up to 824 g h⁻¹ of CO₂.

These results clearly demonstrate that the peak CO₂ demand during the central daylight hours is mainly satisfied by the inorganic carbon supplied with the incoming medium, while the other two major CO₂ sources are atmospheric absorption across the channel and paddlewheel sections. CO₂ absorption in the sump is comparatively less significant because aeration was not continuously applied; however, it remains the only contribution that can be enhanced in raceway ponds by increasing the aeration rate or enlarging the sump volume. If kept constant at 500 L/min, the air flow rate can provide up to 0.73 kgCO₂/day, and thus proportionally increases at higher air flow rates. The analysis of the overall CO₂ accumulation within the system indicates that the buffering capacity of the culture medium plays a central role in regulating CO₂ availability for microalgal cells (Fig. 7B). During the night, CO₂

accumulates in the culture medium, whereas during the daylight period it is consumed through photosynthesis. Consequently, atmospheric CO₂ capture occurs continuously over 24 h, while its biological fixation through photosynthesis takes place exclusively during daylight.

To demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed technology that couples microalgae production with Direct Air Capture (DAC) of atmospheric CO₂, experimental results over a period of four consecutive days with similar solar radiation conditions are presented (Fig. 8). The data validate the operational dynamics of the system, particularly in terms of CO₂ uptake from the atmosphere and CO₂ removal via sump outlet, while maintaining stable pH levels. Furthermore, dissolved oxygen concentrations displayed a consistent diurnal pattern, increasing from approximately 3 mg/L during the night to 30 mg/L during daylight hours, despite continuous aeration used both to supply CO₂ and to regulate oxygen levels. During this experimental period, the biomass

Fig. 7. Hourly CO₂ mass balance in the 600 m² raceway reactor illustrating the main fluxes and accumulation dynamics: (A) CO₂ demand and supply through the culture medium, channel, paddlewheel, and sump during daylight and night periods; and (B) overall carbon balance in the culture showing CO₂ accumulation and consumption patterns as a function of time.

Fig. 8. Temporal evolution of key culture parameters during four consecutive days of continuous operation of the 600 m² raceway reactor under DAC conditions, illustrating the stability of the system over extended operation.

productivity was maintained at an average of 12 g/m²·day. While not exceptionally high, this value is notable given the stress conditions imposed on the culture, particularly high pH and severe carbon limitation. Analytical measurements of Total Inorganic Carbon (TIC) in the culture broth revealed extremely low concentrations—approximately 20 mg/L—confirming that the system operated under conditions of extreme carbon limitation. Nevertheless, the observed productivity was comparable to that of other open raceway systems that use pure CO₂

supplementation, indicating the robustness and resilience of the microalgae under these challenging conditions. These findings provide strong evidence for the technical viability of the integrated microalgae-DAC system, particularly for deployment in remote or resource-limited settings. The ability to maintain biological productivity under ambient air conditions with minimal carbon availability supports its potential role in mitigating global warming and reducing atmospheric CO₂ concentrations through net-negative emissions. This innovative process has

been formally recognized and is protected under patent by the company CHLYDRO (No WO2024245917).

The cost of Direct Air Capture (DAC) technologies remains a subject of intense debate, with reported estimates ranging from \$30 to over \$1000 per ton of CO₂ captured. In contrast, capture costs from flue gases are generally more constrained, typically falling within the \$30–\$100 per ton CO₂ range. A technical assessment by the American Physical Society (APS) in 2011 estimated the net cost of CO₂ capture from air at around \$600 per ton, based on a benchmark system using aqueous sodium hydroxide as the absorbent. Subsequent optimization studies significantly reduced these cost projections to \$518–\$568 per ton with improved packing materials and process configurations, and as low as \$309 per ton when integrating efficient heat recovery, low-cost natural gas, and plastic-based packing elements. The proposed microalgae-based DAC technology, using raceway reactors with sump-based air injection, introduces a novel approach where ambient air is bubbled through the sump to facilitate CO₂ absorption. To overcome the 0.3 bar pressure drop associated with this air delivery, the theoretical energy requirement is estimated at 2.86 kWh per kg of CO₂ captured. Assuming an electricity cost of €0.10 per kWh, this corresponds to an energy-related cost of €285 per ton of CO₂, which is comparable to the lower range of current DAC systems. Naturally, a more detailed economic assessment is required to validate the viability of this approach. However, it is important to note that this system can utilize renewable energy sources, making it particularly promising for remote or off-grid locations.

These findings represent an important first step in the development of robust and scalable microalgae-based systems for atmospheric CO₂ capture. Future work should focus on optimizing operational parameters such as pH and alkalinity to maximize CO₂ uptake, and on refining the carbon balance across the entire reactor, including analyses of biomass composition, dominant algal strains, and adaptive physiological responses. Ultimately, a new generation of reactor designs will be required to accommodate higher airflow rates while maintaining high CO₂ capture efficiency and minimizing energy input, which are key to the long-term sustainability and competitiveness of algal DAC technologies. The incorporation of digital twins and intelligent control methods can further enhance DAC–microalgae integration by enabling adaptive optimization of airflow, light, and pH dynamics [38]. The microalgal biomass produced under DAC conditions is suitable for existing markets such as biofertilizers and biostimulants, animal and aquaculture feed ingredients, and as a feedstock for bioenergy or biorefinery processes, where the additional value associated with atmospheric CO₂ capture can further enhance its economic and environmental relevance.

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrates the feasibility and transformative potential of integrating microalgae cultivation with Direct Air Capture (DAC) of atmospheric CO₂ in large-scale raceway pond reactors equipped with sump-based aeration. The system achieved up to 95% CO₂ removal efficiency while maintaining continuous biomass production exclusively from ambient air, confirming the capability of *Scenedesmus* sp. to sustain growth under extreme carbon limitation and alkaline conditions. Despite operating at moderate productivity (12 g m⁻² day⁻¹), these results establish the technical proof of concept for bio-DAC as a dual-function process that simultaneously removes CO₂ from air and generates valuable biomass. The estimated energy demand for air bubbling (≈ 2.9 kWh kg⁻¹ CO₂) is comparable to or below that of current engineered DAC systems, highlighting the competitive advantage of this biologically integrated approach in terms of simplicity, cost, and compatibility with renewable energy sources. The integration of natural CO₂ fixation with passive gas–liquid mass transfer mechanisms opens a new pathway toward decentralized and carbon-negative biotechnologies. Future developments should target optimization of sump hydrodynamics, airflow distribution, and pH buffering, coupled with renewable-powered

operation and biomass valorization strategies. These advances will enable scalable deployment of bio-DAC systems as a sustainable, low-energy alternative for atmospheric CO₂ mitigation and circular bio-resource production.

Authors contribution

R. Arraga designed and conducted the experiments, performed data collection and analysis of CO₂ mass transfer and carbon balance, and led the manuscript writing and figure preparation.

M. Barceló-Villalobos contributed to the experimental setup and reactor operation, assisted with data interpretation, and participated in manuscript drafting and critical revisions.

R. Esteite supported the analytical methodology, performed calculations of energy demand and CO₂ capture efficiency, and contributed to data validation and discussion.

M. Ahaddouch assisted with mass transfer modeling, equilibrium calculations, and preparation of graphical results, and contributed to manuscript editing.

C. Sánchez-Salinas developed the data acquisition and control architecture, managed SCADA integration, and contributed to analysis of the monitoring data.

F. G. Acíen conceptualized the study, coordinated the research activities, secured funding, supervised all stages of the work, and finalized the manuscript for submission.

All authors reviewed and approved the final manuscript.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

M. Ahaddouch: Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **R Esteite:** Writing – original draft, Software, Formal analysis. **F.G. Acíen:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **C. Sánchez-Salinas:** Validation, Supervision, Software. **R. Arraga:** Methodology, Investigation. **M. Barceló-Villalobos:** Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have influenced the work reported in this manuscript.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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